

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MEHARI****FIRST NAME: ZELELEM****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the main goal of ACA-401/ACA-401D course?

- To improve your English writing skills.
- To teach you how to write academic papers.
- To prepare you for international academic writing.
- All of the above.¹**

2. What are the key elements of a publishable-grade academic paper?

- Logical flow, proper citations, and original research.²**
- Long paragraphs, complex sentences, and big words.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 3.

² Ibid., 7.

- Lots of direct quotes, personal opinions, and emotional language.
 - Short paragraphs, simple sentences, and colloquial language.
3. Dissertation Draft Focus: For a dissertation following Turabian Guidelines, what is a crucial aspect to consider during the initial drafting stage?
- Experimentation and data collection.
 - Depth of literature review.**³
 - Inclusion of personal opinions.
 - Length of the abstract.
4. Argument Development Strategies: According to Turabian, what strategy should a student employ to develop a nuanced and sophisticated argument in a dissertation?
- Prioritize quantity of evidence over quality.
 - Avoid using counterarguments to maintain clarity.
 - Present only evidence that supports the thesis.
 - Acknowledge and engage with opposing viewpoints.**⁴
5. Scope Management: How does Turabian guide researchers in managing the scope of their arguments to ensure depth and specificity?
- Focus on breadth rather than depth for comprehensiveness.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27.

⁴ Ibid., 61.

- Include all relevant information to cover all bases.
- Clearly define the scope and limitations of the argument.**⁵
- Rely on external factors to determine scope.

6. Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Data: What is a potential challenge in integrating quantitative and qualitative findings?

- Limited methodological diversity.
- Increased clarity in research outcomes.
- Simplification of data interpretation.
- Difficulty in reconciling disparate results.**⁶

7. Data Collection and Analysis: What is a potential challenge in using participant observation as a data collection method?

- Observer bias.**⁷
- Lack of ecological validity.
- Difficulty in recruiting participants.
- Limited researcher involvement.

8. Research Design: What is the primary advantage of an experimental research design?

⁵ Ibid., 65–67.

⁶ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 7.

⁷ Ibid., 41.

- Improved ecological validity.
- Greater generalizability.
- Enhanced control over variables.**⁸
- Increased external validity.

9. What is the primary purpose of the WHO style guide?

- To provide a set of writing rules for WHO staff.
- To ensure consistency across all WHO publications.**⁹
- To provide a reference for language and style in health-related documents.
- All of the above.

10. What does the WHO style guide say about the use of footnotes?

- They should be used for asides and tangential information.
- They should be used for essential information only.
- They should be avoided.
- They should be used for references and citations.**¹⁰

⁸ Ibid., 62.

⁹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide*, Second edition (WHO, 2013), 1.

¹⁰ Ibid., 53.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations : Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

WHO. *WHO Style Guide*. Second edition. WHO, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.